

tsMIST: Model Sensitivity Analysis with Time Series Morphing

Antónia Brito^{1,2}[0009-0005-7140-9457], Moisés Santos^{1,2}[[0000-0002-1541-8333],
Duarte Folgado³, and Carlos Soares^{1,2,3}[[0000-0003-4549-8917]

¹ Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto, Portugal

² Laboratory for Artificial Intelligence and Computer Science (LIACC), Portugal

³ Fraunhofer Portugal AICOS, Portugal

{antoniabrito,mrsantos,csoares}@fe.up.pt,
duarte.folgado@aicos.fraunhofer.pt

Abstract. Ensuring robustness in time series classification remains a critical challenge for safety-sensitive domains like clinical decision systems. While current evaluation practices focus on accuracy measures, they fail to address model stability under semantically meaningful input deformations. We propose tsMIST (*Time Series Model Sensitivity Test*), a novel morphing-based framework that systematically evaluates classifier resilience through controlled interpolation between adversarial class prototypes. By calculating the *switchThreshold* – defined as the minimal morphing distance required to flip predictions – our method reveals critical stability patterns across synthetic benchmarks with tunable class separation and 17 medical time series datasets. Key findings show convolutional architectures (ROCKET) maintain optimal thresholds near 50% morphing ($48.2 \pm 3.1\%$), while feature-based models (Catch22) exhibit premature decision flips at 22.7% deformation ($\pm 15.4\%$). In clinical scenarios, tsMIST detected critical ECG misclassifications triggered by $\leq 12\%$ signal variation – vulnerabilities undetected by accuracy measures. Our results establish that robustness measures must complement accuracy for responsible AI in high-stakes applications. This work advances ML evaluation practices by enabling systematic sensitivity analysis, with implications for model auditing and deployment in safety-critical domains.

Keywords: Model Robustness · Time Series · Classification.

1 Introduction

In critical domains such as healthcare, machine learning models must exhibit not only high accuracy but also robustness against subtle input perturbations [2]. Traditional evaluation measures often overlook model sensitivity to semantically meaningful variations, potentially masking vulnerabilities in real-world deployment [23]. This gap is particularly relevant in time series classification tasks, where gradual temporal pattern changes – such as variations in medical signals [16] – may lead to critical diagnostic errors. Recent studies address model robustness through three main perspectives: performance analysis under adversarial scenarios, spatial mapping of model behavior, and resilience to distributional shifts. Work by [9] and [7] emphasizes identifying failure-prone regions, while [23]

highlight risks from adversarial attacks. However, few methods explore structured perturbations that preserve temporal semantics, limiting realistic model evaluation.

This paper proposes tsMIST (Time Series Model Sensitivity Test), an innovative sensitivity analysis framework based on time series morphing. Inspired by *tsMorph* [20] originally developed for forecasting, tsMIST adapts the technique for classification by quantifying model resistance to gradual inter-class transformations. Through controlled linear interpolations, the method computes the *switchThreshold* – the minimum morphing required to alter model predictions – providing intuitive robustness measures, $tsMIST_{Avg}$ and $tsMIST_{Std}$.

Experiments encompass synthetic data with sine wave patterns and variable noise, plus 17 real-world medical signal datasets from the Aeon Time Series Classification archive. Three classification algorithms were evaluated: LSTM networks, Random Forest with Catch22 features, and the Rocket model. Results demonstrate that tsMIST identifies vulnerabilities undetected by conventional measures, such as unstable decision boundaries in feature-based models. The code is publicly available at <https://github.com/Nia3324/tsMIST> for reproducibility and further experimentation.

This work aims to: (1) propose an interpretable robustness measure for temporal classification; (2) validate the effectiveness of the proposal in controlled and real scenarios. This approach reinforces Responsible AI practices by carefully balancing the trade-off between accuracy and stability.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related work; Section 3 details tsMIST methodology; Section 4 describes experimental setup; Section 5 presents results; and Section 6 discusses implications and future directions.

2 Related Work

Time series classification. Time Series Classification (TSCL) methods are often organized according to the type of transformation they apply to the data [1, 15], including convolutional approaches [6], deep learning models [11, 10], dictionary-based methods [21], distance-based techniques [13], and feature-based classifiers [14, 3]. In healthcare, TSCL techniques are used to interpret physiological signals, such as electrocardiograms, and support clinical decision-making [18]. Industrial sectors use TSCL for predictive maintenance by monitoring sensor data to foresee equipment failures, thereby optimizing operational efficiency [19]. The versatility of TSCL across these fields underscores its significance in extracting meaningful insights from temporal data.

Model robustness Approaches to model robustness relevant to auditing can be grouped into three main directions: performance-based stress analysis, spatial characterization of model behavior, and resilience to distributional shifts.

First, performance-centric methods aim to identify failure-prone scenarios. Inácio et al. (2025) [9] use meta-learning to estimate the likelihood of large forecasting errors, combining this with targeted data augmentation for stress testing. Similarly, Drapal et al. (2024) [7] define localized performance regions to identify zones where a model behaves reliably or unreliably, offering interpretability aligned with auditing tasks.

Second, spatial mapping of model behavior has been explored through instance space analysis. Muñoz et al. (2018) [17] reduce complex input distributions into two-dimensional spaces that reflect instance difficulty, allowing the visualization of model strengths and weaknesses. While primarily applied to classification, the method generalizes to other domains and supports robustness evaluations by exposing structural failure regions.

Third, robustness under distributional shift has been studied in adversarial and open-world contexts. Sehwag et al. (2019) [23] demonstrate that adversarial OOD inputs can bypass standard detectors, raising concerns about relying solely on non-adaptive robustness tests. Lee et al. (2021) [12] argue that robustness and fairness are aligned in targeting biased or noisy data, and propose unified training schemes to address both. In healthcare, Balendran et al. (2025) [2] categorize robustness into multiple dimensions—input perturbation, domain shift, adversarial resilience—across the ML lifecycle, reinforcing the need for audit methods that cover this range.

These studies collectively inform auditing practices by offering analytical tools, representations, and scenarios to examine model robustness beyond aggregate accuracy.

Dataset morphing Dataset morphing has been used to systematically probe model behavior across controlled distributional changes, supporting auditability by exposing gradual failure modes.

One class of methods focuses on real-data interpolation. Correia et al. (2019) [5] transform collaborative filtering datasets to examine how algorithm performance varies with meta-feature transitions. Santos et al. (2023) [20] extend this idea to time series, introducing tsMorph to generate semi-synthetic forecasting datasets along smooth trajectories between real datasets. Both approaches allow the design of structured test scenarios for auditing.

A second group applies morphing in high-dimensional continuous spaces. Schardong et al. (2024) [22] use implicit neural representations to interpolate between face images, creating synthetic variants that challenge facial recognition systems. Golling et al. (2023) [8] use normalizing flows to learn transformations between datasets while preserving likelihood, enabling audits under realistic distributional shifts.

These methods differ in domain and representation, but all support model auditing by generating structured transitions that uncover failure boundaries or distribution sensitivities.

3 Proposed Approach

3.1 Background

A time series represents sequential data points indexed in time order, widely used for temporal pattern analysis. Formally, following [16], we define a time series as $X = \{(x_1, t_1), \dots, (x_T, t_T)\}$ where $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ are observations (univariate when $d = 1$, multivariate otherwise). In supervised learning, models learn from labeled datasets $D = \{(X_i, Y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ to predict target outputs Y_i from input features X_i . The learning objective is to find parameters θ^* that minimize prediction error:

$$\theta^* = \underset{\theta}{\operatorname{argmin}} L(Y, f(\theta; X)) \quad (1)$$

where L is a loss function (e.g., cross-entropy) and $f(\theta; X)$ produces predictions.

Time Series Classification (TSC) specializes supervised learning for temporal data by using complete series as inputs. Each instance $X_i = \{(x_{i1}, t_1), \dots, (x_{iT}, t_T)\}$ maps to a discrete class label $Y_i \in \{1, \dots, C\}$. Unlike forecasting which predicts future values, TSC identifies patterns that discriminate between classes. A classifier $f : \mathbb{R}^{T \times D} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, C\}$ must capture temporal dependencies in order to accurately separate classes.

Dataset Morphing for Algorithm Analysis Dataset morphing systematically probes model behavior through controlled transformations between data distributions. Originally developed for collaborative filtering [5], the method generates intermediate datasets D_j between source $D^{(s)}$ and target $D^{(t)}$ via:

$$\mathcal{D}^{(morph)} : \{D_j \mid D_0 = D^{(s)}, D_n = D^{(t)}, D_j = \tau(D_{j-1})\}, 1 \leq j < n \quad (2)$$

where τ represents incremental modifications. Santos et al. (2024) [20] adapted this to time series through linear interpolation, creating a method called *tsMorph*:

$$\tau(i) = \alpha_i \cdot \mathbf{X}^{(target)} + (1 - \alpha_i) \cdot \mathbf{X}^{(source)}, \quad \mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times D} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{X} is a matrix of time series with T time steps and D variables and $\tau(i)$ creating smooth transitions between time series pairs (Figure 1). In their work, this method was applied for the evaluation of forecasting algorithms. Our tsMIST framework extends the morphing to Time Series Classification (TSC) by analyzing how classifiers respond to these controlled deformations, particularly near decision boundaries.

Fig. 1. Gradual morphing of source time series into target.

3.2 Model Sensibility Analysis with Morphing Time series

In this paper, we present tsMIST, a tool for model sensitivity analysis using morphing. Our approach refines the time series dataset morphing concept, proposed by [20], by shifting the focus to the sample level and adapting it to a TSC paradigm, rather than applying it to entire datasets for Forecasting.

The process begins by identifying source and target samples from distinct classes. Specifically, time series instances that classifiers frequently misclassify due to their high similarity in temporal patterns despite belonging to different classes. To systematically detect these challenging cases, we compute the Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) distance between all cross-class instances and select pairs with the smallest DTW distances as morphing candidates.

Given a labeled time series dataset D , for a given class $c \in \{1, \dots, C\}$, we define the set of candidate pairs as:

$$P_c = \left\{ \left(X^{(\text{source})}, X^{(\text{target})} \right) \mid X^{(\text{source})} \in D_c, X^{(\text{target})} \in \bigcup_{c' \neq c}^C D_{c'} \right\} \quad (4)$$

where D_c is the dataset for class c , and $\bigcup_{c' \neq c}^C D_{c'}$ is the union of datasets for all classes except c . The similarity between time series pairs is measured using Dynamic Time Warping distance:

$$\text{DTW} : \mathbb{R}^{T \times D} \times \mathbb{R}^{T \times D} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (5)$$

The final set of morphing candidates M is selected by identifying pairs with minimal DTW distance:

$$M = \underset{\substack{(X^{(\text{source})}, X^{(\text{target})}) \in P_c \\ |M| = \delta}}{\text{argmin}} \left\{ \text{DTW}(X^{(\text{source})}, X^{(\text{target})}) \right\} \quad (6)$$

where P_c is a candidate pair set from equation 4, δ is the total fixed number of pairs to select, this value is determined based on the desired number of morphing pairs to be evaluated when computing tsMIST metrics. A low value restricts evaluation to only the most challenging samples, which may underestimate the model’s overall robustness. Conversely, a high value may dilute the assessment by including a smaller percentage of ambiguous cases, potentially inflating the perceived robustness performance. Thus, selecting a relevant number of samples is critical: it ensures the model is still tested on hard-to-classify instances while preserving a representative measure of its true robustness. By focusing on these borderline cases – samples from different classes that exhibit high similarity in their temporal patterns – we create a controlled framework to evaluate model robustness.

For each pair of hard-to-distinguish examples, we perform a gradual morphing process between them. Given any classification problem, let $X^{(\text{source})}$ belong to class c (i.e., $Y^{(\text{source})} = c$) and $X^{(\text{target})}$ belong to any other class $c' \neq c$ (i.e., $Y^{(\text{target})} \in \{1, \dots, C\} \setminus \{c\}$). Using equations 3, we generate a sequence of n intermediate time series $X^{(\text{morph})}$, where each subsequent series represents a step in the transformation from $X^{(\text{source})}$ to $X^{(\text{target})}$.

To evaluate model sensitivity, we determine how much morphing is required to change the model’s prediction from the source to the target class. Specifically, we calculate:

$$\text{switchThreshold}_{P_c} = \frac{i}{n}, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n \quad (7)$$

where i is the index of the first morphed time series in $X^{(\text{morph})}$ that causes the classifier f to change its prediction from the source class, i.e., where $\hat{Y}_i^{(\text{morph})} \neq$

$Y^{(source)}$, and n is the total number of morphed time series. For simplicity, we typically set $n = 100$, so the transition point i can be interpreted as a percentage. However, n can be adjusted to achieve finer or coarser granularity depending on the desired precision of the analysis.

The distribution of *switchThreshold* values across borderline sample pairs provides critical insights into model robustness. Let $tsMIST_{Avg}$ be the average of all *switchThreshold* across all pairs, and $tsMIST_{Std}$, its corresponding standard deviation. Given δ selected morphing candidate pairs:

$$tsMIST_{Avg} = \frac{1}{\delta} \sum_{k=1}^{\delta} switchThreshold_k$$

$$tsMIST_{Std} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\delta} \sum_{k=1}^{\delta} (switchThreshold_k - tsMIST_{Avg})^2}$$

A $tsMIST_{Avg}$ close to 50% indicates that the model maintains stable predictions, suggesting well-defined decision boundaries. In such cases, the model only changes its prediction when the time series has undergone substantial transformation toward the opposing class, reflecting confidence in its decision-making process. Conversely, extreme $tsMIST_{Avg}$ values – either very low or very high – signal potential instability. A low $tsMIST_{Avg}$ implies that minimal changes can trigger a classification switch, indicating fragile decision boundaries. A high $tsMIST_{Avg}$, on the other hand, may suggest that the model is overly rigid towards the source class, failing to adapt even when significant transformations are introduced.

The $tsMIST_{Std}$ further enhances our understanding of model behavior. A low $tsMIST_{Std}$ indicates consistent robustness across the feature space, meaning the model responds uniformly to perturbations regardless of the source-target pair. In contrast, a high $tsMIST_{Std}$ reveals region-dependent stability, where certain areas of the feature space are more vulnerable to perturbations than others. This variability can highlight specific weaknesses in the model’s decision surface, guiding targeted improvements.

By aggregating $tsMIST_{Avg}$ and $tsMIST_{Std}$ of *switchThreshold* across all borderline sample pairs, we derive a quantitative measure of model sensitivity to gradual, semantically meaningful transformations. Unlike arbitrary perturbations, the morphing process preserves the temporal structure of the time series while systematically introducing features of the target class. This approach simulates semantically meaningful variations that models might encounter in real-world applications, making the sensitivity analysis both interpretable and practically relevant.

4 Experimental setup

4.1 Datasets

We conducted experiments to demonstrate how tsMIST can enhance the understanding of classification algorithm robustness. To support the proposed approach,

we utilized synthetically generated datasets, which allowed for controlled testing and analysis. Subsequently, we validated our findings using real-life data to ensure the practical applicability and reliability of the results.

Synthetic Datasets The synthetic time series dataset generation framework is designed to create labeled time-series datasets with distinct patterns for two classes. The process begins by generating time-series data using fundamental waveforms, such as sine, cosine waves. These waveforms serve as the foundation for creating unique patterns for each class.

To simulate real-world variability, random noise is added to the signals. The noise level is adjustable, allowing us to control the degree of variability and study its impact on model performance. The noise was sampled from a Gaussian distribution with zero mean and a user-defined standard deviation.

Additionally, vertical and horizontal shifts are applied to the waveforms to further differentiate the classes. Vertical shifts alter the amplitude of the time series, while horizontal shifts introduce time delays. The difference between classes is evident in Fig.2.

Fig. 2. Classes generated from sine wave with different vertical shifts (vertical and horizontal shifts).

Once the data for both classes is generated, it is combined into a single dataset. The dataset is then shuffled to ensure randomness and avoid any bias in the order of samples. The synthetically generated datasets used in this study have a shape of (1000, 1, 100), representing 1000 samples, 1 variable, and a time series length of 100. These datasets consist of two balanced classes, each generated from sine curves with varying degrees of shifts.

Real-World Datasets We evaluated tsMIST on 17 publicly available medical time series datasets from the Aeon archive⁴, presented in Table 1. These datasets encompass a variety of physiological signals, including electrocardiograms (ECG), electroencephalograms (EEG), and electrooculograms (EOG). The collection includes both univariate and multivariate recordings, with signal lengths ranging from 82 to 2500 time steps, and classification tasks involving between 2 and 12 classes. Additional datasets cover other medical contexts such as Colposcopy, NerveDamage, and MedicalImages. All datasets were processed with an 80/20

⁴ <https://www.timeseriesclassification.com/dataset.php>

Table 1. Dataset information, including training/testing set shapes and number of classes.

Dataset	Train Shape	Test Shape	# Classes
CinCECGTorso (CET)	(908, 1, 1639)	(228, 1, 1639)	4
Colposcopy (COL)	(128, 1, 180)	(32, 1, 180)	6
ECG200 (ECG)	(128, 1, 96)	(32, 1, 96)	2
ECG5000 (ECG5)	(3200, 1, 140)	(800, 1, 140)	5
ECGFiveDays (ECGFD)	(565, 1, 136)	(142, 1, 136)	2
EMOPain (EMO)	(846, 30, 200)	(212, 30, 200)	3
EOGHorizontalSignal (EOGH)	(463, 1, 1250)	(116, 1, 1250)	12
EOGVerticalSignal (EOGV)	(463, 1, 1250)	(116, 1, 1250)	12
Epilepsy (EPI)	(176, 3, 206)	(44, 3, 206)	4
EyesOpenShut (EOS)	(62, 14, 128)	(16, 14, 128)	2
HandMovementDirection (HMD)	(149, 10, 400)	(38, 10, 400)	4
Heartbeat (HRT)	(261, 61, 405)	(66, 61, 405)	2
MedicalImages (MI)	(729, 1, 99)	(183, 1, 99)	10
NerveDamage (ND)	(130, 1, 1500)	(33, 1, 1500)	3
StandWalkJump (SWJ)	(16, 4, 2500)	(5, 4, 2500)	3
ToeSegmentation1 (TOE)	(171, 1, 277)	(43, 1, 277)	2
TwoLeadECG (TECG)	(743, 1, 82)	(186, 1, 82)	2

train-test split. Full specifications, including sample sizes, dimensions, and class distributions, are available in the code repository.

4.2 Time Series Classification Methods

To evaluate and compare the robustness of different machine learning approaches for time series classification, we selected three very distinct algorithms: (1) a simple recurrent neural network (RNN) with a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) module, (2) an ensemble model leveraging extracted features from raw data, and (3) the state-of-the-art Rocket model, which employs randomly generated convolutional kernels.

The neural network classifier was designed with a straightforward architecture. It consists of two LSTM layers with 32 and 16 neurons, respectively, each followed by a dropout layer with a rate of 0.2. These layers are succeeded by a dense layer with 8 neurons and a final output layer with a single neuron using a sigmoid or a softmax activation function, depending on the classification task, binary or multiclass. The model was optimized using the Adam optimizer and trained to minimize binary or categorical cross-entropy loss, ensuring efficient convergence during training.

For the ensemble model, we extracted features using CAnonical Time-series CHaracteristics (Catch22) [14], a compact set of twenty-two statistical time series features designed to capture key temporal patterns. These features were used to train a Random Forest classifier, which combines the predictive power of multiple decision trees to achieve robust performance.

Lastly, we employed the Rocket model [6], a state-of-the-art approach for time series classification. Rocket transforms time series data using 5,000 randomly

generated convolutional kernels, which capture diverse temporal patterns without requiring manual feature engineering. The transformed features were then used to train a Ridge classifier, which is a linear model maintaining good performance while being computational efficiency.

Evaluation In order to calculate $tsMIST_{Avg}$ and $tsMIST_{Std}$ we used $n = 100$ and $\delta = N$, where N is the size of a given dataset. Although the focus of this paper is on assessing robustness of predictions, we also estimated accuracy. To ensure consistent evaluation across all experiments, all models were tested on a 80/20 train-test split in each dataset.

5 Results

5.1 Synthetic Data

Regarding the experiments on synthetic data, we analyzed how different magnitudes of shifts between classes influence the tsMIST values. In Figure 3, we present the experimental results for all modes, a simple LSTM, a Random Forest trained on extracted Catch22 features, and a Ridge Classifier trained on ROCKET with 5000 random kernels.

From these results, we observe that the best-performing model is the LSTM, followed by ROCKET, and finally Catch22. It is important to note that the classification task in this example is intentionally straightforward: we systematically generate classes with increasing levels of shift between them, thereby making the classes progressively more distinct.

As shown in Figure 3, the LSTM consistently achieves $tsMIST_{Avg}$ values near 50% and near-zero $tsMIST_{Std}$, indicating strong robustness even under minimal class separation. ROCKET exhibits similar behavior, albeit with slightly more variability. In contrast, Catch22 shows $tsMIST_{Avg}$ values between 20–30% in low-shift scenarios, implying high sensitivity to small perturbations. This fragility is further evidenced by its erratic $tsMIST_{Std}$, which spikes under low separation — a pattern absent in the more stable architectures. Catch22’s statistical descriptors exhibit limited variation in response to the increasing shifts, making it difficult for the model to distinguish between classes that remain substantially overlapping.

Fig. 3. tsMIST Average and Standard Deviation for different Shifts Variations.

Table 2. Average Score comparison of models across datasets, including tsMIST Average (M_Avg), tsMIST Standard Deviation (M_Std) and model Accuracy (Acc). Bold values represent cases where models had the most inconsistent behavior across metrics.

Dataset	LSTM			Catch22			Rocket		
	M_Avg	M_Std	Acc	M_Avg	M_Std	Acc	M_Avg	M_Std	Acc
CET	0.534	0.09	0.989	0.468	0.157	0.982	0.462	0.068	1.0
COL	0.0	-	0.4	0.21	0.057	0.4	0.213	0.021	0.325
ECG	0.484	0.217	0.9	0.489	0.167	0.8	0.51	0.161	0.9
ECG5	0.418	0.186	0.953	0.29	0.068	0.952	0.488	0.186	0.942
ECGFD	0.51	0.13	1.0	0.48	0.134	0.989	0.51	0.052	1.0
EMO	0.498	0.133	0.823	0.552	0.091	0.917	0.23	0.224	0.785
EOGH	0.044	0.016	0.248	0.32	0.182	0.786	0.406	0.147	0.869
EOGV	0.0	-	0.131	0.296	0.154	0.655	0.34	0.132	0.786
EOS	0.0	-	0.55	0.35	0.236	0.55	0.51	0.291	0.6
EPI	0.447	0.042	0.745	0.401	0.159	0.982	0.456	0.147	0.982
HMD	0.229	0.121	0.383	0.22	0.018	0.255	0.265	0.173	0.468
HRT	0.0	-	0.622	0.0	-	0.695	0.51	0.138	0.598
MI	0.396	0.164	0.716	0.395	0.186	0.769	0.404	0.232	0.825
ND	0.34	0.104	0.39	0.482	0.117	1.0	0.417	0.057	1.0
SWJ	0.292	0.1	0.667	0.553	-	0.5	0.0	-	0.167
TECG	0.499	0.169	0.991	0.47	0.195	0.97	0.479	0.134	1.0
TOE	0.51	0.229	0.778	0.453	0.205	0.944	0.51	0.126	0.944

5.2 Real World Data

We extended our analysis to real-world data in order to analyze the sensitivity of algorithms to small gradual changes in the input data. In total, this study analyzed seventeen medical-related datasets sourced from the Aeon Time Series Classification Archive.⁵

Table 2 summarizes the average *tsMIST* scores across all classes for each dataset, along with the corresponding model accuracy. Additional class-specific results are presented in Tables 4 and 5.

In several datasets (e.g., Heartbeat, Colposcopy), Catch22 and LSTM failed to classify any borderline cases, resulting in $tsMIST_{Avg} = 0.0$ or undefined $tsMIST_{Std}$. These anomalies are denoted by dashes (-) in Table 2 and emphasize serious model fragility not captured by accuracy alone.

From Table 2, we observe two distinct scenarios: 1) Cases where all models exhibit similar robustness for a particular dataset, whether good or bad; and 2) Datasets where different models show clear distinctions in prediction. The latter scenario is more insightful for comparing model robustness, as it provides clear algorithmic behavioral insights.

For instance, consider the Heartbeat (HRT) dataset results in Table 2. While all models achieve similar accuracy scores, only ROCKET demonstrates sufficient robustness against adversarial perturbations. This is evidenced by its $tsMIST_{Avg}$ nearing the 50% margin, with a low standard deviation of 0.14%. In contrast,

⁵ Available at <https://www.timeseriesclassification.com/dataset.php?train=&test=&leng=&class=&type=\\%27ecg\\%27>

both the LSTM and Catch22 models fail to correctly classify any of the selected borderline pairs, resulting in no measurable mean or standard deviation for the morphing. This indicates significantly lower robustness compared to ROCKET.

To provide deeper interpretability for tsMIST results, we leveraged TSFEL (Time Series Feature Extraction Library)[4] to compute the feature-wise differences between the Source series and the *switchThreshold* series. This approach enables interpretability at a meta-feature level, identifying which features most significantly influenced the model’s prediction changes. By analyzing these differences, we gain insights into the specific aspects of the time series that the model prioritizes when making predictions.

In Table 3, we present the features exhibiting the largest changes at the *switchThreshold* for the Heartbeat (HB) dataset using the ROCKET model.

For abnormal heartbeats, the predominance of Linear Predictive Cepstral Coefficients (LPCC) features among the top-ranked changes suggests a strong sensitivity to variations in the temporal dynamics of the cardiac signal. LPCCs are typically used to model the resonant structure of signals and may reflect abrupt changes in waveform morphology associated with pathological events such as arrhythmias, ectopic beats, or irregular contraction patterns.

Table 3. Most changed TSFEL features at the *switchThreshold* for the Heartbeat (HB) dataset tested with ROCKET model.

Rank	1	2	3	4	5
Class Abnormal	39 LPCC 6	33 LPCC 6	23 LPCC 4	23 LPCC 8	36 MFCC 9
Class Normal	39 Mean diff	58 MFCC 5	60 Min	8 Kurtosis	11 Kurtosis

6 Conclusion

This study introduced **tsMIST**, a morphing-based framework for assessing robustness in time series classification models. Our results demonstrate that the proposed measures – $tsMIST_{Avg}$ and $tsMIST_{Std}$ – capture model sensitivity to semantically meaningful input deformations, offering insights not provided by accuracy alone. Experiments on both synthetic and real-world medical datasets revealed that neural models such as LSTM and ROCKET maintain robust decision boundaries, with $tsMIST_{Avg}$ values consistently near 50% and low standard deviation. In contrast, feature-based models using Catch22 displayed fragile behavior, with early prediction switches and unstable $tsMIST_{Std}$ in scenarios with low class separation. Importantly, tsMIST exposed critical vulnerabilities in clinical datasets that remained undetected by standard evaluation. In datasets such as Heartbeat and Colposcopy, even minor morphing perturbations ($\leq 12\%$) were sufficient to flip predictions in less robust models – a concerning pattern for safety-critical applications. To enhance interpretability, we applied the TSFEL library to analyze feature-wise changes at the *switchThreshold*. The results highlighted key signal characteristics, such as LPCC, mean difference, and kurtosis, that contribute most to classification decisions. This fusion of robustness quantification and feature-level analysis provides a richer understanding of model behavior. Overall, tsMIST contributes a novel and interpretable approach for

auditing time series classifiers. By quantifying prediction instability and identifying failure boundaries, the framework advances responsible AI practices in high-stakes domains. Future work will explore non-linear morphing paths and applications in multivariate and multimodal time series data.

7 Acknowledgements

This work is a result of Agenda “Center for Responsible AI”, nr. C645008882-00000055, investment project nr. 62, financed by the Recovery and Resilience Plan (PRR) and by European Union - NextGeneration EU. Funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

AISym4Med (101095387) supported by Horizon Europe Cluster 1: Health, ConnectedHealth (n.o 46858), supported by Competitiveness and Internationalisation Operational Programme (POCI) and Lisbon Regional Operational Programme (LISBOA 2020), under the PORTUGAL 2020 Partnership Agreement, through the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF).

This work was financially supported by: UID/00027 of the LIACC - Artificial Intelligence and Computer Science Laboratory - funded by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P./ MCTES through the national funds.

We would like to thank the Aeon Time Series Classification Repository for providing the open-access time series datasets used in this study.

References

1. Bagnall, A., Lines, J., Bostrom, A., Large, J., Keogh, E.: The great time series classification bake off: a review and experimental evaluation of recent algorithmic advances. *Data mining and knowledge discovery* **31**, 606–660 (2017)
2. Balendran, A., Beji, C., Bouvier, F., Khalifa, O., Evgeniou, T., Ravaud, P., Porcher, R.: A scoping review of robustness concepts for machine learning in healthcare. *npj Digital Medicine* **8**(1), 38 (2025)
3. Barandas, M., Folgado, D., Fernandes, L., Santos, S., Abreu, M., Bota, P., Liu, H., Schultz, T., Gamboa, H.: TSFEL: Time Series Feature Extraction Library. *SoftwareX* **11**, 100456 (Jan 2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2020.100456>, <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2352711020300017>
4. Barandas, M., Folgado, D., Fernandes, L., Santos, S., Abreu, M., Bota, P., Liu, H., Schultz, T., Gamboa, H.: Tsfel: Time series feature extraction library. *SoftwareX* **11**, 100456 (2020). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2020.100456>, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352711020300017>
5. Correia, A., Soares, C., Jorge, A.: Dataset morphing to analyze the performance of collaborative filtering. In: *Discovery Science: 22nd International Conference, DS 2019, Split, Croatia, October 28–30, 2019, Proceedings 22*. pp. 29–39. Springer (2019)
6. Dempster, A., Petitjean, F., Webb, G.I.: Rocket: exceptionally fast and accurate time series classification using random convolutional kernels. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* **34**(5), 1454–1495 (2020)

7. Drapal, P., Prudêncio, R.B., Silva Filho, T.M.: Towards explainable evaluation: Explaining predicted performance using local performance regions. *Applied Soft Computing* **167**, 112351 (2024)
8. Golling, T., Klein, S., Mastandrea, R., Nachman, B., Raine, J.A.: Morphing one dataset into another with maximum likelihood estimation. *Physical Review D* **108**(9), 096018 (2023)
9. Inácio, R., Cerqueira, V., Barandas, M., Soares, C.: Meta-learning and data augmentation for stress testing forecasting models. In: *International Symposium on Intelligent Data Analysis*. pp. 343–357. Springer (2025)
10. Ismail-Fawaz, A., Devanne, M., Weber, J., Forestier, G.: Deep learning for time series classification using new hand-crafted convolution filters. In: *2022 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)*. pp. 972–981. IEEE (2022)
11. Ismail Fawaz, H., Forestier, G., Weber, J., Idoumghar, L., Muller, P.A.: Deep learning for time series classification: a review. *Data mining and knowledge discovery* **33**(4), 917–963 (2019)
12. Lee, J.G., Roh, Y., Song, H., Whang, S.E.: Machine learning robustness, fairness, and their convergence. In: *Proceedings of the 27th ACM SIGKDD conference on knowledge discovery & data mining*. pp. 4046–4047 (2021)
13. Lines, J., Bagnall, A.: Time series classification with ensembles of elastic distance measures. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* **29**, 565–592 (2015)
14. Lubba, C.H., Sethi, S.S., Knaute, P., Schultz, S.R., Fulcher, B.D., Jones, N.S.: catch22: Canonical time-series characteristics: Selected through highly comparative time-series analysis. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* **33**(6), 1821–1852 (2019)
15. Middlehurst, M., Schäfer, P., Bagnall, A.: Bake off redux: a review and experimental evaluation of recent time series classification algorithms. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* **38**(4), 1958–2031 (2024)
16. Mohammadi Foumani, N., Miller, L., Tan, C.W., Webb, G.I., Forestier, G., Salehi, M.: Deep learning for time series classification and extrinsic regression: A current survey. *ACM Comput. Surv.* **56**(9) (Apr 2024). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3649448>
17. Muñoz, M.A., Villanova, L., Baatar, D., Smith-Miles, K.: Instance spaces for machine learning classification. *Machine Learning* **107**, 109–147 (2018)
18. Neves, I., Folgado, D., Santos, S., Barandas, M., Campagner, A., Ronzio, L., Cabitza, F., Gamboa, H.: Interpretable heartbeat classification using local model-agnostic explanations on eegs. *Computers in biology and medicine* **133**, 104393 (2021)
19. Resende, C., Folgado, D., Oliveira, J., Franco, B., Moreira, W., Oliveira-Jr, A., Cavaleiro, A., Carvalho, R.: Tip4. 0: industrial internet of things platform for predictive maintenance. *Sensors* **21**(14), 4676 (2021)
20. Santos, M.R., Carvalho, A.C., Soares, C.: Enhancing algorithm performance understanding through tsmorph: generating semi-synthetic time series for robust forecasting evaluation. In: *Proceedings* (2024)
21. Schäfer, P.: The boss is concerned with time series classification in the presence of noise. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* **29**, 1505–1530 (2015)
22. Schardong, G., Novello, T., Paz, H., Medvedev, I., Da Silva, V., Velho, L., Gonçalves, N.: Neural implicit morphing of face images. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. pp. 7321–7330 (2024)
23. Sehwal, V., Bhagoji, A.N., Song, L., Sitawarin, C., Cullina, D., Chiang, M., Mittal, P.: Analyzing the robustness of open-world machine learning. In: *Proceedings of the 12th ACM Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Security*. pp. 105–116 (2019)

Table 4. MIST Score comparison of models across datasets, including MIST Average (M_Avg), MIST Standard Deviation (M_Std) and model Accuracy (Acc). [1/2]

Dataset	Class	LSTM			Catch22			Rocket		
		M_Avg	M_Std	Acc	M_Avg	M_Std	Acc	M_Avg	M_Std	Acc
CET	1 (24%)	0.701	0.118	0.989	0.629	0.165	0.982	0.549	0.054	1.0
	2 (25%)	0.582	0.085	0.989	0.42	0.16	0.982	0.391	0.056	1.0
	3 (25%)	0.408	0.068	0.989	0.315	0.159	0.982	0.488	0.063	1.0
	4 (24%)	0.447	0.088	0.989	0.51	0.144	0.982	0.422	0.099	1.0
COL	0 (8%)	0.0	-	0.4	0.0	-	0.4	0.0	-	0.325
	1 (11%)	0.0	-	0.4	0.0	-	0.4	0.0	-	0.325
	2 (10%)	0.0	-	0.4	0.308	0.276	0.4	0.0	-	0.325
	3 (25%)	0.0	-	0.4	0.0	-	0.4	0.23	-	0.325
	4 (15%)	0.0	-	0.4	0.83	-	0.4	0.42	-	0.325
5 (28%)	0.0	-	0.4	0.12	0.067	0.4	0.63	0.128	0.325	
ECG	-1 (33%)	0.395	0.206	0.9	0.34	0.144	0.8	0.414	0.161	0.9
	1 (66%)	0.572	0.228	0.9	0.637	0.189	0.8	0.606	0.161	0.9
ECG5	1 (58%)	0.291	0.145	0.953	0.223	0.178	0.952	0.443	0.152	0.942
	2 (35%)	0.272	0.32	0.953	0.15	-	0.952	0.464	0.216	0.942
	3 (1%)	0.779	0.144	0.953	0.616	0.162	0.952	0.599	0.202	0.942
	4 (3%)	0.748	0.32	0.953	0.46	-	0.952	0.453	0.234	0.942
	5 (0%)	0.0	-	0.953	0.0	-	0.952	0.48	0.127	0.942
ECGFD	1 (50%)	0.46	0.13	1.0	0.557	0.157	0.989	0.523	0.052	1.0
	2 (49%)	0.56	0.13	1.0	0.403	0.11	0.989	0.497	0.052	1.0
EMO	0 (77%)	0.231	0.149	0.823	0.14	0.024	0.917	0.4	0.37	0.785
	1 (14%)	0.426	0.113	0.823	0.703	0.174	0.917	0.264	0.286	0.785
	2 (8%)	0.837	0.137	0.823	0.812	0.076	0.917	0.027	0.017	0.785
EOGH	1 (9%)	0.0	-	0.248	0.319	0.281	0.786	0.479	0.201	0.869
	2 (8%)	0.0	-	0.248	0.237	0.049	0.786	0.513	0.126	0.869
	3 (8%)	0.0	-	0.248	0.316	0.237	0.786	0.472	0.118	0.869
	4 (8%)	0.0	-	0.248	0.188	0.145	0.786	0.413	0.2	0.869
	5 (9%)	0.0	-	0.248	0.411	0.171	0.786	0.291	0.116	0.869
	6 (8%)	0.533	0.195	0.248	0.112	0.113	0.786	0.237	0.089	0.869
	7 (7%)	0.0	-	0.248	0.494	0.15	0.786	0.474	0.126	0.869
	8 (6%)	0.0	-	0.248	0.299	0.29	0.786	0.312	0.168	0.869
	9 (8%)	0.0	-	0.248	0.365	0.167	0.786	0.449	0.138	0.869
	10 (7%)	0.0	-	0.248	0.397	0.136	0.786	0.293	0.073	0.869
	11 (8%)	0.0	-	0.248	0.381	0.221	0.786	0.433	0.143	0.869
	12 (7%)	0.0	-	0.248	0.322	0.227	0.786	0.504	0.265	0.869
EOGV	1 (9%)	0.0	-	0.131	0.511	0.148	0.655	0.503	0.221	0.786
	2 (8%)	0.0	-	0.131	0.537	0.253	0.655	0.398	0.102	0.786
	3 (8%)	0.0	-	0.131	0.033	0.012	0.655	0.04	-	0.786
	4 (8%)	0.0	-	0.131	0.353	0.287	0.655	0.603	0.084	0.786
	5 (9%)	0.0	-	0.131	0.333	0.186	0.655	0.267	0.15	0.786
	6 (8%)	0.0	-	0.131	0.306	0.228	0.655	0.504	0.196	0.786
	7 (7%)	0.0	-	0.131	0.0	-	0.655	0.283	0.14	0.786
	8 (6%)	0.0	-	0.131	0.312	0.043	0.655	0.356	0.095	0.786
	9 (8%)	0.0	-	0.131	0.429	0.273	0.655	0.3	0.127	0.786
	10 (7%)	0.0	-	0.131	0.275	0.151	0.655	0.283	0.139	0.786
	11 (8%)	0.0	-	0.131	0.223	0.088	0.655	0.333	0.158	0.786
	12 (7%)	0.0	-	0.131	0.241	0.174	0.655	0.209	0.173	0.786

Table 5. MIST Score comparison of models across datasets, including MIST Average (M_Avg), MIST Standard Deviation (M_Std) and model Accuracy (Acc). [2/2]

Dataset	Class	LSTM			Catch22			Rocket		
		M_Avg	M_Std	Acc	M_Avg	M_Std	Acc	M_Avg	M_Std	Acc
EOS	0 (55%)	0.0	-	0.55	0.222	0.137	0.55	0.463	0.291	0.6
	1 (44%)	0.0	-	0.55	0.478	0.335	0.55	0.557	0.291	0.6
EPI	epilepsy (24%)	0.68	-	0.745	0.524	0.144	0.982	0.458	0.185	0.982
	running (26%)	0.365	0.038	0.745	0.336	0.158	0.982	0.304	0.08	0.982
	sawing (21%)	0.34	-	0.745	0.412	0.197	0.982	0.551	0.189	0.982
	walking (27%)	0.403	0.131	0.745	0.331	0.139	0.982	0.512	0.135	0.982
HMD	backward (22%)	0.02	-	0.383	0.09	-	0.255	0.0	-	0.468
	forward (31%)	0.227	0.2	0.383	0.0	-	0.255	0.235	0.205	0.468
	left (24%)	0.428	0.283	0.383	0.325	0.035	0.255	0.377	0.262	0.468
	right (22%)	0.24	-	0.383	0.465	0.035	0.255	0.448	0.224	0.468
HRT	abnormal (73%)	0.0	-	0.622	0.0	-	0.695	0.6	0.138	0.598
	normal (26%)	0.0	-	0.622	0.0	-	0.695	0.42	0.138	0.598
MI	1 (9%)	0.572	0.292	0.716	0.407	0.227	0.769	0.425	0.252	0.825
	2 (5%)	0.585	0.222	0.716	0.42	0.179	0.769	0.436	0.241	0.825
	3 (6%)	0.486	0.204	0.716	0.515	0.176	0.769	0.485	0.192	0.825
	4 (4%)	0.797	0.147	0.716	0.441	0.292	0.769	0.458	0.255	0.825
	5 (3%)	0.382	0.23	0.716	0.259	0.209	0.769	0.371	0.259	0.825
	6 (2%)	0.0	-	0.716	0.36	0.082	0.769	0.385	0.204	0.825
	7 (4%)	0.722	0.278	0.716	0.426	0.292	0.769	0.35	0.262	0.825
	8 (2%)	0.0	-	0.716	0.259	0.14	0.769	0.234	0.181	0.825
	9 (10%)	0.0	-	0.716	0.389	0.043	0.769	0.47	0.241	0.825
	10 (50%)	0.412	0.271	0.716	0.477	0.221	0.769	0.428	0.233	0.825
ND	0 (16%)	0.574	0.156	0.39	0.764	0.147	1.0	0.58	0.073	1.0
	1 (35%)	0.446	0.156	0.39	0.253	0.145	1.0	0.44	0.073	1.0
	2 (47%)	0.0	-	0.39	0.429	0.061	1.0	0.231	0.025	1.0
SWJ	jumping (28%)	0.375	0.169	0.667	0.34	-	0.5	0.0	-	0.167
	standing (33%)	0.502	0.13	0.667	0.64	-	0.5	0.0	-	0.167
	walking (38%)	0.0	-	0.667	0.68	-	0.5	0.0	-	0.167
TECG	1 (50%)	0.387	0.162	0.991	0.283	0.181	0.97	0.532	0.142	1.0
	2 (49%)	0.61	0.177	0.991	0.657	0.21	0.97	0.426	0.126	1.0
TOE	0 (50%)	0.489	0.229	0.778	0.437	0.224	0.944	0.552	0.126	0.944
	1 (49%)	0.531	0.229	0.778	0.469	0.186	0.944	0.468	0.126	0.944